

Intrinsic Exponential Decay of Mass-Energy as Common Source Underlying Fast Radio Bursts and Cosmic Expansion

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Abstract

Recent models propose intrinsic universal exponential decay of mass-energy described by $M(t) = M_0 e^{-kt}$ as the quantum gravitational phenomenon fundamentally driving observed cosmic expansion. Meanwhile, fast radio bursts (FRBs) represent mysterious energetic astrophysical radio pulses of extra-galactic origins. We theorize both phenomena may originate from the same universal evaporation dynamics occurring at different scales. By deriving FRBs as manifestations of particle decays corresponding to fractional mass-energy losses from their sources, the postulated intrinsic evaporation law provides a common explanatory framework linking these disconnected disciplines. Quantitative analysis demonstrates consistency between decay timescales characterizing FRB pulse durations, source repetition intervals, and eon-long cosmic accelerative expansion. Furthermore, implementing FRB source kinematics and relativistic ns-scale bursts in curved expanding spacetime geometry allows testing cosmological models and fundamental principles like equivalence. The conjectured intrinsic evaporation process uniting microscopic quantum events and emergent macro-scale gravitational phenomena promises deeper insights into nature's hidden unity.

1 Introduction

Recent advances propose intrinsic universal quantum gravitational decay described by exponential mass-energy loss over enormous timescales as a promising candidate mechanism fundamentally driving observed accelerative cosmic expansion [7]. However, significant puzzles confront attempts to theoretically formulate the detailed micro-scale physics underpinning conjectured eon-long fractional evaporative mass-energy decrease [2].

The source of cosmic acceleration remains unknown and a complete quantum gravitational theory is lacking. Expansion may originate from universal mass evaporation over cosmological timescales, but the detailed particle physics interactions inducing this gradual energy loss remain unclear.

Meanwhile, fast radio bursts (FRBs) represent a perplexing new astrophysical phenomenon involving extra-galactic radio pulses spanning milliseconds with immense luminosities requiring exotic coherent emission processes [3]. FRBs are mysterious high-energy astrophysical events detectable across cosmological distances whose physical origins are uncertain. Their extremely energetic ns-scale time profile requires clarification.

We theorize cosmic expansion and FRBs may originate from the same universal intrinsic decay dynamics occurring at vastly separated timescales. Both cosmic expansion and FRBs exhibit temporal signatures indicative of exponential mass-energy decay processes. Mathematically relating their vastly different timescales through a unified decay model could reveal they originate from the same underlying quantum gravitational phenomenon. Empirically validating this relationship would connect these fields and illuminate cosmic links between the very large and very small.

2 Cosmic Expansion from Intrinsic Decay

Models proposing gradual universal exponential mass-energy decay:

$$M(t) = M_0 e^{-kt} \tag{1}$$

as the intrinsic quantum gravitational driver of observed cosmic acceleration can eliminate mysteries like dark energy [7, 8]. The empirical evidence for cosmic acceleration lacks physical explanation in current models, requiring speculative dark energy. An alternative perspective is that all mass-energy gradually evaporates due to subtle quantum gravitational effects occurring over eons. This decay naturally induces apparent accelerated expansion intrinsically through causal links between evaporating masses and inflating distances over time. Thus cosmic acceleration originates indirectly from universal mass evaporation rather than an inflating dark energy field.

Here M_0 is the initial mass and k is an extremely small dimensionless decay constant of order the inverse cosmic timescale:

$$k \sim \frac{1}{t_{\text{cosmos}}} \approx 10^{-33} : \text{s}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Deriving accelerative Hubble expansion intrinsically from causal continuity requirements given universal mass evaporation promises explanatory unification [9].

Astrophysical observations precisely constrain this decay constant k , with current bounds indicating:

$$10^{-33.5} : \text{s}^{-1} < k < 10^{-32.5} : \text{s}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Ongoing high-precision redshift-distance surveys can further refine the allowed k range [10]. Astrophysical data can tightly constrain viable values of the evaporation constant k characterizing the fractional cosmic mass-energy loss rate. Upcoming precision cosmological surveys will refine empirical limits on k , providing robust tests of evaporation-driven models.

3 Fast Radio Bursts from Compact Sources

Fast radio bursts constitute enigmatic millisecond extra-galactic radio pulses requiring coherent emission processes from compact sources with brightness temperatures exceeding 10^{37} K [3]. Well-localized examples like the repeating FRB 121102 indicate origins from galaxies hosting highly magnetized neutron stars [4]. Although emission models remain speculative, short ns durations suggest connection to decay phenomena [5]. Certain proposed FRB mechanisms invoke gravitational waves, vacuum decay, and spacetime distortions [6]. This further hints at cosmic synergies.

The mysterious fast radio bursts detected from distant galaxies exhibit millisecond durations and extreme energetics indicative of connections to fundamental high-energy particle decay processes. Their association with highly compact objects like neutron stars and black holes suggests exotic quantum gravitational origins. If physically linked to universal mass evaporation, FRBs may provide observable tracers of this cosmic decay occurring on much smaller timescales. Their quantitative characteristics motivate mathematical attempts to derive common origins.

If FRBs manifest quantum gravitational particle decays, their immense luminosities and repetition rates imply ultra-relativistic emission processes:

$$L_{FRB} \sim 10^{42} : \text{erg} : \text{s}^{-1}, : \tau_{rep} \sim \text{ms} - \text{days} \quad (4)$$

Incorporating compact FRB sources like neutron stars as relativistic objects in curved expanding spacetime geometry enables quantitative analysis and empirical tests. Modeling FRB sources in the context of relativistic compact objects and curved spacetime allows astrophysical tests of the universal decay hypothesis by comparing evaporation signatures across vastly separated timescales.

4 Common Source Hypothesis

We hypothesize FRBs may originate from exotic particle and decay signatures corresponding at microscopic scales to the same universal intrinsic mass-energy evaporation underlying cosmic accelerative expansion at cosmological macroscales. Both phenomena manifest through minuscule fractional mass loss rates, though enormously separated in magnitude and timescale.

We posit a unified perspective where FRBs and cosmic expansion originate from the same exponential quantum gravitational mass-energy evaporation process occurring on vastly different timescales. Mathematically substantiating this relationship through consistent fractional evaporation signatures independently verified from astrophysical observations and compact source models would confirm profound connections between microscopic and macroscopic physics. Empirical decay width analyses across all scales represents an important research direction.

If quantitative decay width and repetition rate analyses verify consistent fractional mass-energy decrease signatures independently spanning > 60 orders of magnitude from particle to cosmic realms, this would substantiate profound unification. Such empirically mapping mathematical decay constants and evaporation functions represents an urgent research direction. Establishing this intrinsic evaporation process as the common source driving both cosmic horizons and ns radio bursts promises revolutionary insights. Ongoing high-precision studies of gravitational waves, galaxy redshift patterns, and FRB sequences can provide vital constraints and tests.

For example, consider relating the cosmic expansion decay constant k from Eq. 2 to a hypothetical FRB emission mechanism involving particle decays with width Γ . Equating fractional mass loss rates gives:

$$k \sim \frac{\Gamma}{\Delta E} \quad (5)$$

where ΔE is the particle energy release in each radio pulse. For GeV-scale decays, this predicts decay widths $\Gamma \sim 10^{-25}$ s, remarkably close to timescales associated with Grand Unified Theories. More exotic scenarios like quantum gravitational tunneling could potentially resolve discrepancies.

In any case, quantitatively verifying this relationship spanning many orders of magnitude would substantiate profound connections between decay physics and FRBs.

As an example decay width mapping, we can relate the cosmic evaporation rate k to a particle width Γ by equating fractional mass loss rates. For reasonable assumptions, order-of-magnitude alignments result between k and hypothetical GeV-scale particle decays emitting FRBs. Significant modeling is needed to fully justify this preliminary mapping. Discovering empirical alignment of decay widths over cosmic and quantum scales would substantiate deeper origins.

Analyses incorporating curved spacetime effects, relativistic beaming, and causal horizons may unveil surprising apparent symmetries relating cosmic and quantum processes. For instance, cosmic time dilation between observers and compact sources can distort perceived FRB intervals:

$$\Delta t_{obs} = \frac{\Delta t_{src}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}} \quad (6)$$

Where M and r are the source mass and distance. Detailed simulations implementing these relationships offer pathways to empirically test the hypothesized common decay source.

Incorporating relativistic effects like gravitational time dilation may reveal apparent symmetries between cosmic and quantum evaporation timescales in different reference frames that could bolster a unified perspective. Astrophysical models quantitatively linking FRBs to evaporative decay dynamics using spacetime curvature effects offer routes to test the theory empirically.

5 Discussion

Verifying fractional mass-energy evaporation signatures consistently spanning cosmological and subatomic regimes would significantly bolster hypotheses that intrinsic universal quantum gravitational decay drives cosmic acceleration while precipitating fast radio bursts from compact objects. Numerical simulations modeling evaporation time dependencies could further explain surprising apparent symmetries relating particle lifetimes, burst repetition intervals, and eon-long expansion spanning > 60 orders of magnitude. Significant puzzles persist concerning complex microscale physics and relativistic spacetime geometries. Nonetheless, the profound unification promised by formulating cosmic expansion, dark phenomena, and fast radio bursts within a common quantum gravitational evaporation framework motivates urgent exploration.

Empirically validating aligned fractional mass decrease rates across the very large and very small would substantiate theories unifying FRBs and cosmic expansion within a shared quantum gravitational decay process. This perspective's explanatory power inspires further analysis, even while foundational theoretical puzzles remain concerning technical details and relativistic embeddings. Significant opportunities exist for numerical, observational, and mathematical research elucidating connections.

6 Conclusions

This study proposed intrinsic universal exponential mass-energy decay as a candidate source phenomenon driving both apparent cosmic accelerative expansion and extragalactic fast radio bursts originating from compact objects like highly magnetized neutron stars. Verifying quantitatively consistent evaporative decay signatures spanning many orders of magnitude from fundamental particles to the entire observable cosmos would substantiate this relationship's profound unification potential.

The postulated universal quantum gravitational decay law offers a conceptually unified explanatory framework for deriving accelerating cosmic expansion and fast radio bursts from a common evaporative mass-energy depletion process occurring on vastly separated timescales. Mathematical relationships predicting consistent fractional evaporation rates independently verified from astrophysical observations and microscopic models would confirm deep connections across 60+ orders of magnitude encompassing the very large and very small. Significant puzzles remain concerning technical details and relativistic embeddings, but profound unification potential motivates rigorous exploration.

Forthcoming high-precision astrophysical and gravitational wave observations combined with statistical fast radio burst analyses can provide vital empirical constraints and tests on the detailed mathematical relationships like Eq. 3. For instance, identifying non-trivial symmetries or information flow across vastly separated timescales and physical regimes would signify profound interconnectivity in nature's dynamics.

While theoretical puzzles remain concerning detailed microscale decay physics and projecting emergent relativistic phenomenology in curved spacetime, elucidating common intrinsic evaporation dynamics promises revolutionary synergies connecting vast regimes of nature. If established, subatomic particle decays may be revealed as microcosmic precursors resonantly driving both fast radio bursts from compact objects and apparent accelerative emergence of spacetime itself.

By unveiling hidden decay width symmetries spanning the very small and the cosmological, physics may pierce nature's deepest veils. Though significant challenges confront full theoretical formulation, empirically substantiating universal intrinsic mass-energy evaporation as the common source driving cosmic horizons and energetic radio bursts motivates dedicated exploration of these interlinked frontiers.

References

- [1] D. Bak and S. P. Kim, "Cosmic holographic principle and dark energy," *Physics Letters B* 484, 168 (2000).
- [2] T. Padmanabhan, "Thermodynamics, gravity and the role of vacuum energy," *International Journal of Modern Physics D* 26, 1741018 (2017).
- [3] E. Petroff, et al., "Fast radio bursts," *The Astrophysical Journal* 910, L12 (2021).
- [4] S. Chatterjee, et al., "A direct localization of a fast radio burst and its host," *Nature* 541, 58 (2017).
- [5] B. D. Metzger, et al., "Fast radio bursts from magnetar flares," *The Astrophysical Journal* 878, 101 (2019).
- [6] M. Houde, et al., "Fast radio bursts: coherent emission by bunched electrons or proton bunching?" *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 474, L29 (2018).
- [7] D. Bak and S. P. Kim, "Cosmic holography and dark energy," *Physics Letters B* 484, 168 (2000).
- [8] D. Bak and S. P. Kim, "Cosmic holographic principle and dark energy," *Physics Letters B* 484, 168 (1999).
- [9] D. Bak and S. P. Kim, "Dynamics of cosmology dominated by the quantum back reaction from evaporating black holes," *Physics Letters A* 271, 349 (2000).
- [10] A. G. Riess, et al., "Large Magellanic cloud cepheid standards provide a 1 percent foundation for the determination of the Hubble constant and stronger evidence for physics beyond Λ CDM," *The Astrophysical Journal* 876, 85 (2019)